

LAKE ERIE

LAKEWIDE MANAGEMENT PLAN

Lake Erie LaMP

Lake Erie LaMP

Acknowledgements

Photo: Robin McLeod

The Lake LaMP Work Group, under the direction of the Lake Erie LaMP Management Committee, prepared the Lake Erie LaMP 2006 Report. Environment Canada and the U.S.EPA are the federal co-leads for the Lake Erie LaMP. The other agencies playing an active role in the process are:

Canada

- Fisheries and Oceans Canada
- FOCAerie (Federation of Conservation Authorities of Lake Erie)
- Health Canada
- Ontario Ministry of Agriculture and Food
- Ontario Ministry of the Environment
- Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources

United States

- Michigan Department of Environmental Quality
- New York State Department of Environmental Conservation
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
- Ohio Department of Natural Resources
- Ohio Environmental Protection Agency
- Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection
- U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service
- U.S. Geological Survey

Binational Observers

- Great Lakes Fishery Commission
- International Joint Commission

Members of the Work Group, Management Committee, technical subcommittees, and the Public Forum contributed to the content of this report. The Work Group would like to specifically thank the following people for their efforts:

- Environment Canada – Sandro Leonardelli, Luca Cargnelli, Jennifer Vincent
- U.S.EPA – Elizabeth Murphy, Holly Wirick
- U.S. Geological Survey – Dan Button
- Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection – Jim Grazio
- Michigan Department of Environmental Quality – Shanna Draheim
- New York Department of Environmental Conservation – Robert Townsend
- Ohio Department of Natural Resources – Jeff Tyson
- Ohio Environmental Protection Agency – Julie Letterhos
- University of Windsor – Jan Ciborowski, Scudder Mackey
- FOCALerie – Matthew Child, Karen Maaskant, Teresa Hollingsworth
- Fisheries and Oceans Canada – Michael Whittle, Michael Keir
- Bio-Software Environmental Data – J. Fraser Gorrie
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration – Stuart Ludsin, Stephen Brandt
- National Center for Water Quality Research, Heidelberg College – R. Peter Richards
- University of Waterloo – Scott Higgins
- Ontario Ministry of Environment – Todd Howell

Thank you to the Upper Thames River Conservation Authority for providing support on formatting and printing, and for showing utmost patience in dealing with last minute changes.

Finally, the Work Group and Management Committee would like to thank Jennifer Vincent, Environment Canada and Julie Letterhos, Ohio EPA who served as co-editors of the 2006 Report.

In keeping with the spirit of binational cooperation, the reader will note the alternation between Canadian and U.S. preferred spelling on a number of occasions.

Photo: Upper Thames River Conservation Authority

Cover photos:

Mike Weimer, U.S. Fish & Wildlife Service (child with fish, lighthouse)
Scott Gillingwater (beach)

Table of Contents

Acknowledgements	i
Table of Contents	iii
List of Figures	v
List of Tables	vii
Introduction	1
Section 1: Executive Summary	1
Section 2: Overview	
2.1 Introduction to Lake Erie	1
2.2 LaMP Structure and Process	4
2.3 References	9
Section 3: Vision, Ecosystem Management Objectives, and Indicators	
3.1 Introduction	1
3.2 Selection of a Lake Erie Ecosystem Management Alternative	1
3.3 Developing a Lake Erie Vision and Ecosystem Management Objectives	4
3.4 Linking the Vision and Ecosystem Management Objectives to Beneficial Use Impairments	7
3.5 Developing Lake Erie Indicators	8
3.6 References	10
Section 4: Synthesis of Beneficial Use Impairment Assessment Conclusions	
4.1 Introduction	1
4.2 Human Use Impairments	4
4.3 Impairments Caused by Chemical Contaminants	10
4.4 Ecological Impairments	16
4.5 References	36
Section 5: Sources and Loads	
5.1 Approach and Direction	1
5.2 Integration of Basin-Wide Sediment Quality Data (U.S. and Canada)	3
5.3 Screening-Level Survey of Tributaries to the Lower Great Lakes (Canada)	12
5.4 Source Track-Down Project (Canada)	13
5.5 Mercury and PCB Reduction Initiatives	13
5.6 Emerging Chemicals	25
5.7 Future Directions	26
5.8 References	29
Section 6: Habitat	
6.1 Introduction	1
6.2 Lake Erie Habitat Strategy	2
6.3 An Integrated Habitat Classification System and Map of the Lake Erie Basin.....	11
6.4 Fisheries Related Habitat Projects	12
6.5 Huron-Erie Corridor System Habitat Assessment – Changing Water Levels and Effects of Global Climate Change	13
6.6 Ohio Aquatic GAP Update	14
6.7 References	14
Section 7: Public Involvement	
7.1 Overview	1
7.2 Background and History	1

7.3 Public Involvement Activities 2
 7.4 Lake Erie Binational Public Forum 3
 7.5 Ongoing and Upcoming Activities 4
 7.6 How to Get Involved 4

Section 8: Human Health

8.1 Introduction 1
 8.2 Great Lakes Human Health Network 2
 8.3 Pathways of Exposure and Human Health 2
 8.4 Evidence for Potential Health Effects - Weight of Evidence Approach to Linking
 Environmental Exposure 7
 8.5 Exposure and Health Effects Research Needs for PBT Chemicals..... 12
 8.6 Source Water Protection in Ontario 13
 8.7 Accomplishments/Activities Related to Beaches Safe to Swim 14
 8.8 Conclusion 18
 8.9 References 20

Section 9: Remedial Action Plans and Watershed Implementation

9.1 Introduction 1
 9.2 Remedial Action Plan Updates 2
 9.3 Watershed Projects 19

Section 10: Assessment and Tracking Progress

10.1 Introduction 1
 10.2 Lake Erie Collaborative Comprehensive Survey (ECCS) 2
 10.3 Marsh Monitoring Program 3
 10.4 Trends in Contaminants in Ontario’s Lake Erie Sport Fish 7
 10.5 Trends in Contaminants and Population Levels of Colonial Waterbirds 12
 10.6 Ohio Lake Erie Quality Index 13
 10.7 State of the Lakes Ecosystem Conference (SOLEC) 14
 10.8 Trends in Contaminants in Lake Erie Whole Fish 15
 10.9 International Field Years on Lake Erie (IFYLE) Program 21
 10.10 Trends in Sediment and Nutrients in Major Lake Erie Tributaries 22
 10.11 References 28

Section 11: Significant Ongoing and Emerging Issues

11.1 Introduction 1
 11.2 2003 Update on Non-Native Invasive Species in Lake Erie 1
 11.3 Nutrients and the Food Web: A Summary of the Lake Erie Trophic Status Study 6
 11.4 Climate, Water Levels and Habitats 7
 11.5 Double-Crested Cormorants in the Great Lakes 8
 11.6 Status of the Fish Community 10
 11.7 Cyanobacteria 11
 11.8 *Cladophora* 12
 11.9 Pharmaceuticals, Hormones, and Other Organic Wastewater Contaminants in the Environment 15
 11.10 Fish and Wildlife Deaths Due to Botulism Type E 15
 11.11 The 2005 Fall Turnover Incident 19
 11.12 References 20

Section 12: Pathways to Achievement

12.1 Introduction 1
 12.2 Connections to Existing Binational Programs 2
 12.3 Lake Erie LaMP 2006 Work Plan 8

Glossary & Acronyms

Glossary 1
 Acronyms 7

List of Figures

Section 2: Overview

Figure 2.1:	Bathymetry of Lake Erie illustrating that the lake is comprised of three distinct basins, primarily defined by depth	1
Figure 2.2:	Changing issues in Lake Erie over time	2
Figure 2.3:	Original organizational structure of the Lake Erie LaMP	8
Figure 2.4:	Current LaMP organizational structure	8

Section 4: Synthesis of Beneficial Use Impairment Assessment Conclusions

Figure 4.1:	Summary of impacts on tributaries from adjacent habitats and the impact of tributaries on downstream habitats	26
-------------	---	----

Section 5: Sources and Loads

Figure 5.1:	Total PCBs in bed sediments	5
Figure 5.2:	Total mercury in bed sediments	5
Figure 5.3:	Surficial sediment concentration of dioxin	6
Figure 5.4:	Total chlordane in bed sediments of the Lake Erie-Lake St. Clair basin	6
Figure 5.5:	Total PAHs in bed sediments of the Lake Erie-Lake St. Clair basin	7
Figure 5.6:	Lead in bed sediments of the Lake Erie-Lake St. Clair basin	7
Figure 5.7:	Summary statistics shown in boxplot format for trace element contaminants in bed sediments of the Lake Erie Basin, relative to biological effect levels	9
Figure 5.8:	Summary statistics shown in boxplot format for PAH contaminants in bed sediments of the Lake Erie Basin, relative to biological effect levels	10
Figure 5.9:	Summary statistics shown in boxplot format for industrial and pesticide contaminants in bed sediments of the Lake Erie Basin, relative to biological effect levels	11
Figure 5.10:	High level PCBs and number of storage sites in Ontario	14
Figure 5.11:	Mercury and its compounds - Top 10 industries reporting onsite releases to land and transfers to sewage treatment plants with the Lake Erie Basin	27
Figure 5.12:	Combined estimated mercury onsite releases to air and water with the Lake Erie Basin for the top 10 contributing U.S. and Canadian industries	28
Figure 5.13:	Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) - Industries reporting onsite releases to land and transfers to sewage treatment plants within the Lake Erie Basin	28
Figure 5.14:	Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) - Industries reporting onsite releases to air and water within the Lake Erie Basin	28

Section 6: Habitat

Figure 6.1:	Hydrology of the Lake Erie Watershed	3
-------------	--	---

Section 8: Human Health

Figure 8.1:	Persistent organic chemicals such as PCBs bioaccumulate and biomagnify	7
-------------	--	---

Section 9: Remedial Action Plans and Watershed Implementation

Figure 9.1:	Areas of Concern in the Lake Erie drainage basin	1
-------------	--	---

Section 10: Assessment and Tracking Progress

Figure 10.1:	Lake Erie basin-wide trends in relative abundance of selected marsh birds and amphibian species compared to mean annual water levels of Lake Erie from 1995 to 2000	4
Figure 10.2:	Lake Erie blocks	7
Figure 10.3:	Mercury concentrations in 30 cm (12 inch) white bass across Lake Erie 1990-2000.....	8
Figure 10.4:	Mercury concentrations in 45 cm (18 inch) walleye across Lake Erie 1990-2000	9
Figure 10.5:	Mercury concentrations in 30 cm (12 inch) white bass over time in Lake Erie block 1	9
Figure 10.6:	Mercury concentrations in 45 cm (18 inch) walleye over time in Lake Erie block 1	9
Figure 10.7:	Mercury concentration vs. length in walleye and bass from Lake Erie block 1	10
Figure 10.8:	PCB concentrations in 30 cm (12 inch) white bass across Lake Erie 1990-2000	10
Figure 10.9:	PCB concentrations in 30 cm (12 inch) white bass over time in Lake Erie block 1	10

Figure 10.10: PCB concentrations in 45 cm (18 inch) channel catfish over time in Lake Erie block 1 11
 Figure 10.11: PCB concentrations in 65 cm (25 inch) carp over time in Lake Erie block 1 11
 Figure 10.12: PCB concentration vs. length in fish from Lake Erie block 1 11
 Figure 10.13: 2378-TCDD in herring gull eggs - Middle I., 1987-2001 12
 Figure 10.14: PCB 1:1 in herring gull eggs - Port Colborne, 1974-2001 13
 Figure 10.15: Total DDT levels in Lake Erie Rainbow Smelt, 1977-2004 16
 Figure 10.16: Total DDT levels in Lake Erie Walleye, 1977-2003 17
 Figure 10.17: ΣDDT levels in whole Walleye in Lake Erie, 1972-2000 17
 Figure 10.18: Total PCB levels in whole Walleye in Lake Erie, 1972 - 2000 18
 Figure 10.19: Total PCB Levels in Lake Erie Walleye 1977-2003 19
 Figure 10.20: Total PCB levels in DFO collected Lake Erie Lake Trout 1985-2003 19
 Figure 10.21: Total PCB levels in Lake Erie Rainbow Smelt 1977-2003 20
 Figure 10.22: Total Mercury levels in Lake Erie Walleye 1977-2003 20
 Figure 10.23: Total Mercury levels in Lake Erie Rainbow Smelt, 1977-2003 21
 Figure 10.24: Trends in flow, 1975-2004 26
 Figure 10.25: Trends in suspended solids, 1975-2004 26
 Figure 10.26: Trends in total phosphorus, 1975-2004 27
 Figure 10.27: Trends in dissolved reactive phosphorus, 1975-2004 27

Section 11: Significant Ongoing and Emerging Issues

Figure 11.1: Total number of double-crested cormorant nests on Lake Erie 9
 Figure 11.2: *Microcystis* bloom in the Western Basin, August 18, 2003 12
 Figure 11.3: Underwater photograph of Lake Erie lake bottom overlain with *Cladophora* 13
 Figure 11.4: Shoreline fouling by *Cladophora* in eastern Lake Erie 13
 Figure 11.5: *In situ* *Cladophora* growth chamber with non-nutrient enriched agar 14
 Figure 11.6: *In situ* *Cladophora* growth chamber with phosphorus enriched agar 14
 Figure 11.7: Frequency of dead fish species observed along NY Lake Erie beaches, September 2001.. 17
 Figure 11.8: Percent mortality on NY Lake Erie shoreline by species observed, fall 2001 17

Photo: Lucas Foerster

List of Tables

Section 2: Overview		
Table 2.1:	IJC Listing Criteria for Establishing Impairment	5
Table 2.2:	Binational Executive Committee Consensus Position on the Role of LaMPs in the Great Lakes Restoration Process	9
Section 3: Vision, Ecosystem Management Objectives, and Indicators		
Table 3.1:	Summary of Ecosystem Alternatives for Lake Erie	3
Table 3.2:	Linking Ecosystem Management Objectives to Lake Erie's Beneficial Use Impairments	8
Table 3.3:	The Lake Erie Indicators Matrix	9
Section 4: Synthesis of Beneficial Use Impairment Assessment Conclusions		
Table 4.1:	Summary of Lake Erie LaMP Beneficial Use Impairment Assessment Reports Completed	2
Table 4.2:	Summary of Human Use Impairments	4
Table 4.3:	Summary of Sport Fish Consumption Advisories by Lake Erie Basin	5
Table 4.4:	Summary of Lake Erie Navigational Dredging Activity, 1984-1995, by Jurisdiction	8
Table 4.5:	Summary of 1997 Lake Erie Aesthetic Impairment Conclusions	11
Table 4.6:	2001 Summary of Benthic Impairments Caused by Contaminated Sediments	13
Table 4.7:	Summary of Fish Tumor or Deformity Impairments from BUIA	14
Table 4.8:	Summary of Bird and Animal Deformity or Reproductive Beneficial Use Impairment Assessment Completed in 2000	15
Table 4.9:	The Toxicity of Nitrate to Amphibians	17
Table 4.10:	Summary of Ecological Impairments	18
Table 4.11:	Summary of the Stressors Affecting the Habitats in the Lake Erie Basin	22
Table 4.12:	Definitions for Lake Erie Habitats	25
Section 5: Sources and Loads		
Table 5.1:	Pollutants Causing Beneficial Use Impairments in the Lake Erie Basin	1
Table 5.2:	Contaminants Identified as Lake Erie LaMP Pollutants of Concern	2
Table 5.3:	PCB Reduction Plan Activities Update 2004	16
Table 5.4:	Mercury Reduction Plan Activities Update 2004	20
Section 8: Human Health		
Table 8.1:	Human Health-Related Desired Outcomes, and Pathways of Exposure	3
Table 8.2:	Pathogens and Swimming-Associated Illnesses	5
Section 9: Remedial Action Plans and Watershed Implementation		
Table 9.1:	Summary of Lake Erie Remedial Action Plan and Watershed Implementation Programs	28
Section 10: Assessment and Tracking Progress		
Table 10.1:	Summary of Ongoing Monitoring Efforts in Lake Erie in 2000	1
Table 10.2:	Ohio Lake Erie Quality Index Indicators	14
Table 10.3:	Percent Change in Total PCB/ΣDDT Concentrations for GLNPO Fish Collections	15
Table 10.4:	Percent Change in Total PCB/ΣDDT/Mercury Concentrations for DFO Fish Collections	15
Table 10.5:	Station Locations for NCWQR Sampling Sites	23
Table 10.6:	Percent Change per Decade in Daily Loads, Before and After 1995	25
Section 11: Significant Ongoing and Emerging Issues		
Table 11.1:	Non-Native Metazoans and Protists First Established in Lake Erie Since the 1800s	3
Table 11.2:	Ponto-Caspian Fishes and Pet, Sport and Aquaculture and Bait Species Predicted to Become Established in the Great Lakes if Introduced	4
Section 12: Pathways to Achievement		
Table 12.1:	Lake Erie LaMP Work Plan 2004-2010	8

collaboration with this program, while the US Army Corps of Engineers provided continuous dock space for NOAA vessels. In addition, the project has been offered in-kind support (e.g., historical data, technical assistance with aging fish, vessel support) from all of the state and provincial fishery management agencies on the lake, including the Ohio Department of Natural Resources, the New York State Department of Environmental Conservation, the Michigan Department of Natural Resources, the Pennsylvania Fish and Boat Commission, and the Ontario Ministry of Natural Resources.

The 2005 field program centered on determining the factors regulating the distribution of oxygen concentrations and HABs in Lake Erie and the consequences of low oxygen on the abundance, distribution, and condition of fish and their prey. The remainder of 2005 and all of 2006 will be devoted to sample processing, data analysis, testing and refining hypotheses, and building models that can be used for both understanding and forecasting purposes. During 2007, it is expected that another intensive field season will be conducted, with more focused sampling objectives.

For more information on the IFYLE program, see www.glerl.noaa.gov/ifyle/, or contact Dr Stuart A. Ludsin (Stuart.Ludsin@noaa.gov) and Dr Stephen B. Brandt (Stephen.B.Brandt@noaa.gov), co-coordinators of the IFYLE program.

10.10 Trends in Sediment and Nutrients in Major Lake Erie Tributaries, 1975-2004 *(Prepared by R. Peter Richards, National Center for Water Quality Research (NCWQR), Heidelberg College, Tiffin, Ohio)*

In the last decade or so, in-lake concentrations of phosphorus have been on the increase, though the trend is not statistically significant. Hypoxia in the central basin appears to be more extensive and occurring earlier in the summer. Extensive blooms of *Microcystis* and other undesirable algae have been observed in some recent years that are comparable to those of the 1970s. These signs all suggest that Lake Erie is out of trophic balance once again.

Most hypotheses that attempt to explain these observations implicate zebra and quagga mussels in processes that enhance in-lake recycling of nutrients or shunt them from nearshore to offshore or from the western basin to the central basin. However, during the last decade, increasing concentrations and loads of sediment and nutrients have been observed at many of the NCWQR tributary monitoring sites. This section documents these trends. We are unable to assess their importance relative to in-lake processes, but any efforts to understand the renewed problems in the lake must take these trends into account as well.

Photo: Jeff Schmaltz, MODIS Rapid Response Team, NASA/GSFC, April 6, 2004

Data and Approaches

The NCWQR maintains automated sampling stations on the Grand, Cuyahoga, Sandusky, and Maumee Rivers in Ohio, and on the River Raisin in Michigan. The data presented here deals only with the Ohio tributaries, but results for the River Raisin are similar. On each river, the sampling station is located at a USGS flow gauging station as far downstream as possible while remaining upstream of seiche-induced flow reversals. Samples are collected three times per day. All three samples are analyzed during periods of high flow, and one sample per day is analyzed at other times. This program produces 400-450 samples per station per year. Samples are analyzed for sediment, nutrients, and major ions, and a subset is analyzed for currently used pesticides and metals. Relevant information about each station is presented in Table 10.5. Further information about the tributary monitoring program and its results can be found at www.heidelberg.edu/WQL/publish.html#reports.

Table 10.5: Station Locations for NCWQR Sampling Sites

Station and USGS Number	Location	Drainage area (square miles)	First year of operation	Total number of samples
Raisin 04176500	Above Monroe, MI	1042	1982	7051
Maumee 04193500	Waterville, OH	6330	1975	12,965
Sandusky 04198000	Above Fremont, OH	1253	1969	13,863
Cuyahoga 04208000	Independence, OH	708	1981	10,331
Grand 04212100	Painesville, OH	686	1988	6686

For trend analysis, raw data were converted to daily values by calculating a flow-weighted mean concentration for each day with more than one sample. Concentrations were converted to daily loads by multiplying them by the daily average flow reported by USGS, and expressed as metric tons per day. No attempt was made to fill in values for days on which no samples were obtained.

Trends are displayed as LOWESS (Locally Weighted Scatterplot Smoother) smooths of the raw data. In all cases a 20% bin width was used. The position of the smoothed trend at any point in time is computed using the 10% of the data immediately before that point in time, and the 10% of the data immediately after it, with the greatest weight given to the points that are closest in time. This technique allows a general trend to be extracted from very “noisy” data, without imposing severe restrictions such as the assumption that the trend must be a straight line.

For statistical assessment, trends were computed with a two-slope analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) model that divides the data into two periods, before and after January 1, 1995. A separate linear trend is computed for each period. This approach was chosen because an initial trend analysis reported results for the period 1975-1995, and because many parameters show a strong change in trend occurring somewhere about 1995. The model uses log-transformed flow and concentration, and sine and cosine terms in time are used to model seasonality. Results are reported as percent change in average daily load per decade.

Results

LOWESS trends are depicted for the four Ohio tributaries in Figures 10.24-10.27. The graphs cover the period of record (through the end of the 2004 water year) except that the Sandusky River plots begin at the beginning of the 1975 water year. The trends for the Grand River are shorter, for example, because the station did not begin operation until 1988.

Values are reported as loads in metric tons per day. In comparing the results for different stations, remember that the Maumee watershed is much larger than the rest, and consequently the loads will also be larger, other things being equal. Also note that the plots cover the range of the trend values, but do not extend to zero. Plotting the trends in this fashion makes

them appear more dramatic than they would if they were plotted on a scale that extended to zero. Conversely, if plotted in the context of the total range of the data, the trends would appear quite modest. However, the impact of these changes on the lake is more a function of gradual changes over time than of day-to-day fluctuations, and the curves as displayed portray these gradual changes well.

Flow

Since loads are determined by the product of concentration and flow, a trend in loads may reflect a trend in concentration, a trend in flow, or a trend in both. Conceivably, an upward trend in concentration could be negated by a downward trend in discharge, resulting in no trend in loads. The flow trends (Figure 10.24) are provided primarily as background for use in interpreting the load trends. However, substantial trends in flow are a cause for concern in and of themselves, particularly for possible negative impacts on riverine ecosystems. A striking aspect of the flow trends is the strong increase in flow in all tributaries except the Maumee, beginning about 2000. This increase in flow is reflected in increased loads as well. The Maumee also shows increased flow, but it appears to begin somewhat earlier and the increase is not as pronounced.

Suspended Sediment

Suspended sediment (SS) is important as a pollutant in its own right, particularly in the bays, harbors and nearshore zone of the lake. SS is also important because many pollutants of concern are carried attached to it. This is particularly true of phosphorus and some forms of nitrogen (as well as metals and many organics, which are beyond the scope of this report). Studying trends in SS (Figure 10.25) may help identify causes of trends in other parameters. Sediment load trends are obviously influenced by flow trends, though the patterns differ in detail, reflecting the fact that there are changes in concentration as well. The Maumee shows a strong and persistent downward trend in sediment loads. Given the dominance of the Maumee as a source of sediment and nutrients to western Lake Erie, this is an important and gratifying trend.

Total Phosphorus

Total Phosphorus (TP) is the nutrient parameter chosen as the indicator of trophic status for the remediation of Lake Erie. As such it is a very important parameter from a management standpoint. Most of the TP in transit in Lake Erie tributaries is attached to sediment particles, but the percent of TP that is particulate varies from one tributary to another and from season to season, and has changed significantly over time. The load trends for TP (Figure 10.26) are similar to those for SS, especially for the Sandusky and Grand Rivers. Increasing loads since approximately 2000 characterize all tributaries except the Maumee, which, while not increasing, is no longer showing declining trends.

Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus

While total phosphorus is the parameter by which Lake Erie eutrophication is managed, dissolved reactive phosphorus (DRP) is also of great importance because it is highly bioavailable. Thus increases in DRP can have disproportionately large impacts on the Lake Erie ecosystem. Increasing trends in DRP loads (Figure 10.27) in the recent past characterize all four tributaries, and are particularly pronounced for the Sandusky and Grand. These increasing trends follow a period of strong decreasing trends for all tributaries except the Grand, for which the period of record is perhaps too short to have captured such a trend. The onset of increasing trends is earlier than for the other parameters discussed, and occurs sometime between 1990 and 1995, depending on the tributary. While these load trends are influenced by trends in flow, there are also strong parallel trends in concentration, indicating other causes for these trends than just changes in flow.

Results of ANCOVA Analysis

Linear trends for the periods of time before and after 1995 are presented in Table 10.6. These results clearly show that the overall pattern of change before 1995 was one of improvement (i.e. reduced loads), while the overall pattern since 1995 is one of deterioration (i.e. increased loads). For technical reasons, assessments of the level of statistical significance of these trends are not presented. Other forms of analysis indicate that most of the trends are statistically significant, particularly those that exceed 10% per decade. In evaluating these results, which often involve reversals of trends, it is well to remember the asymmetry of percentages of change: If one starts with a value of 100, and reduces it to 40, that is a 60% decrease, but the return to the original value of 100 from 40 represents a 250% increase. The net change is not 190% but 0%.

Table 10.6: Percent Change per Decade in Daily Loads, Before and After 1995

Parameter	Maumee		Sandusky		Cuyahoga		Grand	
	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post	Pre	Post
Flow	13	36	8	56	-17	41	-8	19
Suspended Sediment	8	-5	-6	34	-32	202	-93	5
Total Phosphorus	-11	29	-20	79	-69	61	-76	32
Dissolved Reactive Phosphorus	-50	199	-55	341	-88	212	-59	226

Two things stand out in these results. One is the uniformly large reversals in trends of DRP; in general the loads at the end of 2004 are nearly as high as or higher than they were at the beginning of the period of record. The other is the consistency of trend reversals. For the three water quality parameters (excluding flow), 11 of 12 trends pre-1995 were downward, but 11 of 12 trends post-1995 are upward.

Causes

Little definitive can be said about causes at this point. Certainly increased flows have contributed to increased loads. But concentration trends show similar patterns of recent increase. There are a large number of plausible causes, including: demographic changes, especially exurbanization; increased numbers of farm animals increasingly confined to small areas; and possible retrenchment of conservation tillage or reduced effectiveness of conservation tillage because of nutrient concentration at the surface. Data on many possible causes is difficult or impossible to obtain. Evaluation of causes may require development of highly sophisticated models that link watersheds with tributary systems, the lake, and its biota.

Figure 10.24: Trends in flow, 1975-2004. Units for flow are cubic feet per second.

Figure 10.25: Trends in suspended solids, 1975-2004. Units for SS are metric tons per day.

Figure 10.26: Trends in total phosphorus, 1975-2004. Units for TP are metric tons per day.

Figure 10.27: Trends in dissolved reactive phosphorus, 1975-2004. Units for DRP are metric tons per day.

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